

Developing Peace Education Programs for Enhancing Conflict Resolution Skill and Communication Skill.

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Abstract:

This study mainly aimed to develop a Peace Education program and test the enhancement of Conflict Resolution skill and Communication skill through the Peace Education Program. A Quantitative Research method was utilized for the present study. Pre-test and Post-test quasi-experimental designs were used and 62 students were randomly chosen as the sample for the present study. The Peace Education Program Session included cooperative activity for conflict resolution concept activity, Documentary and film, cooperative activity, and collaborative team activity for understanding peace level and identifying the conflicts, implemented for the experimental group. The results show that the Peace Education Program had significantly enhanced Conflict Resolution skill and Communication skill.

Keywords: Peace Education Program, Conflict Resolution Skill and Communication Skill.

Introduction

“Inner tranquillity is the source of peace; there’s no need to search for it externally.” - Buddha.

Peace goes beyond the absence of war; it embodies virtues, attitudes, a commitment to goodness, trust, and justice, as articulated by Spinoza. According to R. D. Laing, Peace Education addresses conflicts and violence on various levels, from the global to the personal, aiming to create just and sustainable futures.

Currently regarded as both a philosophy and a process, Peace Education involves skills such as listening, reflection, problem-solving, cooperation, and conflict resolution. The objective is to empower individuals with the skills, attitudes, and knowledge required to foster a secure world and construct a sustainable environment. By indirectly challenging prevailing societal violence, Peace Education educates about its causes and introduces alternatives.

Peace Education is the ongoing process of equipping learners with the tools to develop knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes needed for non-violent conflict resolution and peaceful

coexistence with oneself, others, and the environment. It addresses conflicts at intrapersonal, interpersonal, intergroup, local, national, and international levels.

Johan Dewey emphasizes that Peace Education is rooted in active citizenship, preparing individuals for conscientious participation in a democratic society through problem-posing, problem-solving education, and a commitment to transformative action.

As a remedial measure to shield children from the path of violence in society, Peace Education focuses on imparting skills, attitudes, and values essential for creating and sustaining peace. It teaches conflict resolution without resorting to violence, encourages creative thinking, and promotes the application of non-violent methods. Ultimately, Peace Education seeks the holistic development of the child, instilling elevated human and social values, to benefit all of humanity.

Review of Literature

Conflict Resolution Skill:

1.) Bayraktar, Hatice Vatansever; Yilmaz, Kamile Özge (2016) has studied, “Examining Primary School Teachers’ Conflict Resolution Skills Using Various Variables The purpose of this study is to ascertain the degree of conflict resolution proficiency among primary school teachers and whether there are any significant variances in this domain. The scanning model guided the organization of the investigation. The study’s participants are primary school teachers employed by 14 different primary schools, two of which are located in each of the seven geographical zones. According to the findings of this study, When the relationships between teachers’ conflict resolution skills and their demographic properties were examined, a significant difference was discovered between the independent variables of age, duration of service, and compromising approach.

2) Dipali R Mistry, Mamtarani Verma, Shailee N Vyas, SL Kantharia (2014) this research article deals with “Social Networking Among Youth and Their Communication and Conflict Resolution Skills.” New digital media have significantly transformed the communication landscape, particularly for young people. It is found that in India 26 minutes of internet users utilized the net. This study is concerned with the impact of social networking on youth in terms of possible risk, safety, wellness, and skill development because they are still maturing and developing the ability to communicate. attain & implement communication & conflict resolution skill on interpersonal level. The purpose of this study is to investigate how social networking affects first-year MBBS students’ communication and conflict-resolution abilities. According to the report, users now spend a good deal of time on social networking sites in place of more conventional means of contact. Social networking site use encouraged half of the teenagers to be more outgoing, but as one respondent noted, it did not greatly aid in resolving conflicts. nearly half of the participants.

3) Maurya, Ram Shiromani (2017) has studied, “A Study of Conflict Resolution of Secondary School Students through Peace Education. This paper main objective To identify the determinants

of Conflicts among secondary school students and To study the effect of Peace Education on Conflict Resolution powers of secondary school students. Method of the research Mixed approach as both qualitative and quantitative method has been used in the study. To study the effectiveness of peace education lesson plans, single group pre-test and post-test. the pre-experimental method was used. The mean difference between the pre and post-test scores was not found significant for the dimension related to religious aspects and work is worship.

4) Ketki Satpute (2019) Has studied, “Use Innovative Strategies for Developing a Culture of Peace” The main aim of the research is to study the Use of Innovative strategies for Developing a Culture of Peace. To prepare innovative strategies for developing a culture of peace. The experimental research method uses to the camper the pre-test and post-test scores of the control and experimental group on the development of a culture of peace related to values, attitudes, skill, sharing game film clipping, Art and Drama, Meditation, Autosuggestion on Bed college students’ conclusion of the findings there is a significant difference is the pre-test score of the control group and experimental group of development of a culture of pre-test and post-test in the dimension of Value and Attitudes. There is no significant difference in the pre-test score of the control group and the Experimental group of the development of a culture of peace with respect to the dimension “Skills”

5) Rakhi Dhingra (2015) Has Studied “A comparative study of Awareness and Attitude towards Peace Education among different college teachers. This study was a comparison of awareness and attitude toward peace Education among different college teachers of social science, medical science, and engineering and education fields. Using Descriptive Sampling Techniques, 547 teachers were interviewed as random samples for the study. It was found that there was no significant difference in the comparison of awareness and attitude toward Peace Education among different college teachers.

Need and Rationale of the Study

Education is a powerful mechanism in bringing about peaceful and silent social changes, which results in the sustainable development of society. Peace Education is a process that prepares students for global responsibility which enables them to understand the nature and implications of global interdependence and helps them to accept responsibility by eradicating human ills ranging from injustice, inequality, prejudice, intolerance, abuse of human rights, environmental destruction, violent conflict and so forth to create a world of justice and peace. From such literature, the researcher gets guidance and inspiration. From such literature, researcher taught that were fewer studies conducted on degree college students’ enhancement in conflict resolution skill and communication skill through peace education programs. It is most important to investigate and understand how different strategies can be more widely adopted and effectively used by students to equip them. Students with knowledge and understanding of peaceful relationships help to promote the development of attitudes and a wide range of skills that help students cope effectively with the challenges of everyday life and make more good communication skill or conflict-free life. Hence there is a need to conduct this research.

Aim of the Study

To study the Enhancement of Conflict Resolution Skill and Communication Skill through Peace Education program

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test scores of control group and experimental group of the development of Conflict Resolution Skill.
2. There is no significant difference in the pre-test scores of control group and experimental group of the development of Communication Skill.
3. There no significant difference in the pre-test score of control group and experimental group of Enhancement of conflict resolution among degree college students with respect to following dimension.
 - A) Aggressive Behaviour
 - B) Problem Solving
- 4) There is no significant difference between pre-test score of of control group and experimental group of Enhancement of Communication Skill among degree college students with respect to following dimension.
 - A) Cognitive
 - B) Emotional
 - C) Behaviour
5. There is no significant difference in the post-test scores of control group and experimental group of the development of Conflict Resolution Skill.
6. There is no significant difference in the post-test scores of control group and experimental group of the development of Communication Skill.
7. There no significant difference in the post-test score of control group and experimental group of Enhancement of conflict resolution among degree college students with respect to the following dimension.
 - A) Aggressive Behaviour
 - B) Problem Solving

8. There is no significant difference between a post-test score of control group and the experimental group of Enhancement of Communication Skill among degree college students with respect to the following dimension.

- A) Cognitive
- B) Emotional
- C) Behaviour

Methodology

For the Present study, the Quantitative Research Approach was utilized for the pre-test and post-test. A quasi-experimental design was used for the present study.

Population and Sample for the Study

The population for the present study consists of degree college students. 62-degree college students were randomly chosen and were placed in experiment and control groups.

Tools Used for the Study

For the present study before and after the program, the self-made Scale of Determining the Conflict Resolution Skill and Scale of Communication Skill.

Testing of Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis 1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test scores of conflict resolution skill of control group and the Experimental group.

Table 1 - T-Test of conflict resolution skill Pre-Control and Experimental group of Students

	GROUP	MEAN	SD	T RATIO	SIGNIFICANCE p <0 .05.
Conflict Resolution Skill	CONTROL	238.38	38.49821	1.6522	not significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	225.741	18.25813		

Interpretation:

The obtained t value is 1.6522 for conflict resolution skill at 0.05 level of no significance. The null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion:

There is no significant difference shown in the pre-test control group and experimental group of Conflict Resolution Skill. The experimental group mean score is higher than the control group. It means that the experimental group is more as compared to the control group for Conflict Resolution skill.

Discussion:

There is no significant difference in the pre-test score of the control group and experimental group of enhancement of conflict Resolution skill at 0.05 level. There is no significant difference between the experimental and control group the null hypothesis is accepted.

Null Hypothesis 2 There is no significant difference in the pre-test of control group and experimental group of Communication Skill.

Table 2 - T-Test of Communication Skill Pre-Test Control and Experimental group of Students.

PRE-CONTROL AND EXPERIMENTAL TEST

	GROUP	MEAN	SD	T RATIO	SIGNIFICANCE p <0 .05.
Communication Skill	CONTROL	178.774	28.14097	0.075033	not significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	178.322	18.25813		

Interpretation:

The obtained t value is 0.07 for conflict resolution skill at 0.05 level of no significance. The null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion:

There is no significant difference shown in the pre-test control group and experimental group of Conflict Resolution Skill. A mean score is equal for the control group and the experimental group. It means that the experimental group is equal to the control group only point-wise difference is shown in both groups.

Discussion:

There is no significant difference in the pre-test score of the control group and experimental group of enhancement of conflict Resolution skill at 0.05 level. it may be because

the students of the experimental group and control group for the pre-test conducted after the new admission process is done and fresh mood after the covid period so everyone is new and fresh for the first year with face-to-face learning experience.

Null Hypothesis 3 There no significant difference in the pre-test score of control group and experimental group of Enhancement of conflict resolution among degree college students with respect to following dimension.

- A) Aggressive Behaviour
- B) Problem Solving

Table No. 3 - T Test of conflict resolution skill sub-scale aggressive behaviour and problem-solving Pre Control and Experimental group of Students.

PRE-CONTROL AND EXPERIMENT TEST					
	GROUP	MEAN	SD	T RATIO	SIGNIFICANCE
					p <0 .05.
Aggressive	CONTROL	124.032	18.0175	1.088	not significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	118.258	12.6174		
Problem-Solving	CONTROL	114.419	22.176	1.3671	not significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	107.483	17.498		

Interpretation:

The table shows the obtained t value 1.088 at 0.05 level is not significant for the Aggressive Behaviour sub-scale and t value 1.36 at 0.05 level is not significant for the problem-solving sub-scale.

Conclusion:

The table shows that there is no significant difference between the experimental and control group. It can be seen that the aggressive behaviour mean score is higher than the experimental group which is 124.03 for the control group and 118.25 mean scores for the experimental group. problem-solving sub-scale control group mean score is higher than the experimental group which is 114.41 for the control group and 107.48 for the experimental group. Both sub-scale t-ratios show no significant difference between the control and Experimental group.

Discussion:

It can be seen that the aggressive behaviour sub-scale control group and experimental group t ratio is 1.088 is not significant. It can be also seen that the t ratio is 1.3671 and there is no significant difference between the problem-solving of the control group and the experimental group of a pre-test. It means the null hypothesis is accepted.

Null Hypothesis 4 There no significant difference in the pre-test score of the control group and experimental group of Enhancement of Communication Skill among degree college students, concerning the following dimension.

- A) Cognitive
- B) Emotional
- C) Behaviour

Table No 4 - T-Test of communication skill sub-scale cognitive, emotional and behaviour dimension Pre-Control and Experimental group of Students.

PRE-CONTROL AND EXPERIMENT TEST					
	GROUP	MEAN	SD	T RATIO	SIGNIFICANCE(p <0 .05.)
Cognitive	CONTROL	59.87096	9.999	-0.869	not significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	61.8064	7.6263		
Emotional	CONTROL	59.41935	9.2006	-2.339169	not significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	63.4838	6.5973		
Behaviour	CONTROL	59.48387	11.04799	2.8262	not significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	53.03225	7.1623		

Interpretation:

The table shows the obtained t ratio -0.869 at 0.05 level is not significant for the cognitive dimension, Emotional dimension t ratio -2.33 at 0.05 level is for at 0.05 level is not

significant for the control and experimental group. It can be seen t ratio 2.8262 at 0.05 level is not significant.

Conclusion:

The table shows that there is no significant difference between the experimental and control group. It can be seen that the cognitive mean score is higher for the experimental group that is 61.80 for the experimental group and 59.87 for the control group. The emotional mean score is higher for experimental group is higher than control group which is 63.48 for the experimental group and 59.41 for control group. Behaviour dimension control group mean is higher than experimental group which is 53.03. it can be seen all three dimensions is show differences in t ratio between the control and experimental group.

Discussion:

It can be seen that the control group and experimental group t ratio is -0.869 for the cognitive Dimension, -2.339169 for the Emotional Dimension, and 2.8262 for the Behaviour Dimension at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis is accepted for the pre-test control and experimental group.

Null Hypothesis No 5. There is no significant difference in the post-test scores of Conflict Resolution skill of the control group and the Experimental group.

Table No. 5 - T-Test of conflict resolution skill Post Control and Experimental group of Students.

POST CONTROL AND EXPERIMENTAL TEST					
	GROUP	MEAN	SD	T RATIO	SIGNIFICANCE p <0 .05.
Conflict Resolution Skill	CONTROL	178.4839	21.1358	6.1697	Significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	222.322	33.44287		

Interpretation:

The table shows that after completion of the PEP (Peace Education Program), the researcher observed that there is a significant difference in the control and experimental group in the Conflict Resolution skill scale at the level of p < 0.05 t - ratio 6.1697.

Conclusion:

Table shows that the mean difference is higher for the control group and lower for the experimental group (control mean is $x=178$ and experimental mean is $x = 222.322$).

Discussion:

It can be seen that the mean difference is higher for the experimental group ($x=222.322$) null hypothesis is rejected. It can be seen that PEP (Peace Education Program) the learning environment affects students' behaviour. The experimental group's Mean is higher than the control group it can be found that the learning activity about conflict resolution like based on intro social. After the program the post-test result shows that, the null hypothesis was rejected. The mean difference is higher for the experimental group. It is found that students understood the root of conflict and fighting for fair with a calm attitude and sense of empathy that is the most important things to maintain behaviour. Problem-solving with collaboration and compromise gives more clarity to Handel the problem with peace. The finding shows that the peace education program enhances Conflict Resolution Skill in the experimental group. Students understand how conflict arises and due to miscommunication conflicts occur. Not every conflict is bad may be conflict as an opportunity to survive or to face issues with a balanced mind. It may enhance the skill of problem-solving. Students understood the cause and sometimes humans suffer a lot due to social, economic, political, educational and health-related issues like mental and physical. Through the peace education program, they realized how to behave in a balanced mind and short the problem.

Null Hypothesis No.6. There is no significant difference in the post-test of control group and experimental group of Communication Skill.

Table No.6 - T Test of communication skill Post Control and Experimental group of Students.

POST-CONTROL AND EXPERIMENTAL TEST					
	GROUP	MEAN	SD	T RATIO	SIGNIFICANCE p <0 .05.
Communication Skill	CONTROL	237.096 8	27.27069	13.5321	not significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	169.548 4	18.97865		

Interpretation:

The table shows that after completion of the PEP (Peace Education Program), the researcher observed that there is a significant difference in the control and experimental group in the Communication skill scale at the level of $p < 0.05$ t - ratio 13.5321.

Conclusion:

Table shows that the significant mean difference is higher for the control group and lower for the experimental group (control mean is $x=237.0968$ and experimental mean is $x = 169.5484$). mean score significantly shows the difference between the control and experimental group.

Discussion:

The researcher found a significant difference in Communication Skill 13.5321. The mean difference is higher for the control group and lower for the experimental group (control mean is $x= 237.09$ and experimental mean is $x = 169.54$). The null hypothesis is rejected of Communication Skill. The researcher found that the students gave an exam in the first semester and after that exam, they field the scale and it may be difficult to cope and maybe the impact of stress on their proper cognition to select the response of their natural behaviour. Due to examination brain and stress factors may be affected because the brain plays an important role to managing and controlling human emotions. Part of the Amygdala closely context with fear, anger, or aggression. If in the environment humans encode messages of anger or stress this factor is controlled by the amygdala part. If people damage this area, it gets trouble to balance their emotions, specifically anger and aggression. This part of the brain that's responsible for emotion [what you feel], thoughts [what you have imagined] and behaviour [choice]. The brain function controls emotions, anger and stress. Prefrontal context manages cognitive behaviour expression and decision-making and modifying correct social behaviour. But they solve or complete the tasks that are important things they understood from the peace education program.

Null Hypothesis 7 there is no significant difference in the post-test score of control group and experimental group of Enhancement of conflict resolution skill among degree college students with respect to following dimension.

A) Aggressive Behaviour

B) Problem-Solving

Table No. 7. - T Test of conflict resolution skill sub-scale aggressive behaviour and problem-solving Post Control and Experimental group of Students.

POST CONTROL AND EXPERIMENT TEST					
	GROUP	MEAN	SD	T RATIO	SIGNIFICANCE
					at p <0.05.
Aggressive	CONTROL	121.6452	15.081	0.3427	not significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	116.0968	16.563		
Problem-Solving	CONTROL	115.4516	14.34071	2.09396	significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	106.2258	19.90429		

Interpretation:

Researcher found not significant difference for the Aggressive sub-scale ($x = 116.0968$) at the level of $p < 0.05$ t - ratio is 0.3427. The researcher observed the Problem-Solving sub-scale at the level of $p < 0.05$ t- ratio is 2.09396.

Conclusion:

The table shows that the Aggressive behaviour control group mean score indicates 121.64 and the experimental group post-test mean score is 116.09. It can be seen that there is the mean score of the control group is higher than the experimental group. For the problem-solving scale significant difference show in the control and experimental group.

Discussion:

It can be seen that the mean difference is higher for the control group and lower for the experimental group (control mean is $x = 121.6452$ and experimental mean is $x = 116.0968$) null hypothesis is accepted. The researcher observed the Problem-Solving sub-scale at the level of $p < 0.05$ t- ratio is 2.09396. The mean difference is higher for the experimental group ($x = 106.2258$) null hypothesis is rejected. It is because the students faced the exam of the first semester and after that exam, they field the scale and it may be difficult to cope and maybe the impact of stress on their proper cognition to select the response of their natural behaviour. Students can experience stress and anxiety because of exam and assignments. The duration of the paper 2 or 3 hours after the examination they fill these tools due to examination stress and may be unhappiness often influences the action in comprehensive response. This environment may feel negative. Students' gestures and stressful actions reflect on their response in tools. Most of the students responded in some time for the experimental group. For problem-solving students give responses the items like 'To avoid conflict, I try to compromise' Most of students

give response on the sometimes option and few respond on always that option. Hypothesis accepted for the Dimension. It is found there is no significant difference in the post-test score of the control group and experimental group of Enhancement of conflict resolution skills among degree college students concerning dimension the of Aggressive Behaviour. Hypothesis rejected for the Dimension, it found there is no significant difference in the post-test score of the control group and experimental group of Enhancement of conflict resolution skill among degree college students with respect for the dimension the Problem-Solving.

Null Hypothesis 8 There no significant difference in the post-test score of control group and experimental group of Enhancement of Communication Skill among degree college students concerning the following dimension.

- ❖ Cognitive
- ❖ Emotional
- ❖ Behaviour

Table No.8 - T-Test of communication skill Post Control and Experimental group of Students.

POST-CONTROL AND EXPERIMENT TEST					
	GROUP	MEAN	SD	T RATIO	SIGNIFICANCE(at p <0.05.)
Cognitive	CONTROL	62.645	9.307	1.67256	not significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	58.806	8.757		
Emotional	CONTROL	62.0645	7.261	1.965	significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	58.677	6.231		
Behaviour	CONTROL	53.774	7.77	0.9144	not significant
	EXPERIMENTAL	52.064	6.97		

Interpretation:

The table shows that participants in the PEP enhanced. The researcher also found that the Cognitive dimension showed no significant difference in the control group and experimental group at the level of $p < 0.05$ t - ratio is 1.6725. The researcher found the emotional dimension a significant difference in the control and experimental group at the level of $p < 0.05$ t - ratio is 1.965 The researcher found that the Behaviour dimension not significant difference in control group and experimental group at the level of $p < 0.05$ t - ratio is 0.9144.

Conclusion:

The table shows that the cognitive dimension mean score is higher than the experimental group which is 62.64 for the control group and 58.80 for the experimental group which t ratio is 1.67256 of post-test experimental and control group which shows that no significant difference in the control group and experimental group. It can be seen that the emotional mean score dimension is 62.06 for the control group and mean score of the experimental group is 58.67 and the t ratio is 1.96 this shows a significant difference between the control group and the experimental group of post-tests of students. The behaviour dimension control group mean score is 53.77 and the Experimental group mean score is 52.064 their also seen that t ratio is 0.91 which shows no significant relationship between the post-test control and experimental group.

Discussion:

Table shows that cognitive dimension mean score difference is higher for the control group and lower for the experimental group (control mean is $x=62.645$ and experimental mean is $x = 58.806$) null hypothesis is accepted. The cognitive dimension Mean score is lower show because of examination stress mental capability, intellect, imagination, thinking emotions and other mental processes may be affected. maybe they are not in the proper sense to make decisions to take a proper response that's why they tick without thinking much randomly they choose options. It matters their conscious goals and purposes were examined and may that things affected their ability to enhance to adapt to this kind of environmental condition. Already they had stress but the social emotional system and cognitive control systems have brains that contribute to managing dual tasks. which is what they had learned from the activity. It's also realizing due to exam stress students' responses get affected which can be seen through charts and such items Without knowing facts, before giving any advice, I pay attention to the other person is willing to accept my advice.

The pie charts show the proportion of communication skill for cognitive dimension items like, 'I can communicate my thoughts easily' after the activity post-test conducted on the duration of examination such an item where they can easily think maybe examination stress. it can see in the proportion of responses on sometimes option 32.25% .

Pre-test pie chart

post-test pie chart

The pie charts show the proportion of Interpersonal Communication Skill cognitive dimension. The proportion of pre-test students most of selected the option of always is 41.93%, response for sometimes 22.58%. post-test pie chart report shows the response of always option proportion show 38.70% and for the sometimes option 35.48% proportion seen from the chart report. It also found that for positive statements but it also found that in complex situations they complete their tasks but due to examination their natural reasoning and decision-making ability are affected by stress and anxiety.

The Emotional dimension mean difference is higher for the control group and lower for the experimental group (control mean is $x = 62.0645$ and experimental mean is $x = 58.677$) t ratio of emotional 1.69 shows a significant relationship which means the null hypothesis is

rejected. the significant difference shown in an emotional dimension that is because of the learning environment. Emotions are one aspect of interpersonal communication. Emotion is a major factor in our capacity for successful communication. The most effective communicators display passion, desire, enthusiasm, trust, and composure while constructively utilizing emotion. It is a normal human characteristic for our emotions to obstruct our communication, giving away our feelings and making it difficult to communicate effectively, thus this is a talent that must be mastered. It has been found that students increase their awareness of emotions, sensitivity to their own emotions, persistence and self-motivation even though they had faced examination part they respond at list they show their innate potential to what exactly they feel and also continue to do tool task this is one positive said but it also found that after examination anxiety about next paper and the day of examination economics paper was there and may they not much cope with their emotion feeling due to anxiety of exam they randomly select the option.

Such items like if I am angry with someone, I stay calm while talking to them. There are positive items and students gave responses so it can be seen that, 22.58% of students responded on sometimes. 22.58% of students responded on rare option and 29.03% of students responded on always so students with stress here found their random responses. Also, they face this kind of conflict they resolve by managing their stress positively.

The researcher observed that the mean difference with the dimensions of Aggressive, problem-solving, Cognitive, Emotional, and Behavioural is higher for the control group and lower for the experimental group. It was also found that after completion of the Peace Education Program, there was a significant difference between the experimental and control group in terms of conflict resolution and students showed positive behaviour in handling both tasks it shows a positive impact of the peace education program on conflict resolution and Communication Skill.

DISCUSSION:

Currently, the pursuit of peace is seen as a prerequisite for development, improved living conditions and a better foundation for future generations. From this research, the researcher observed that at the global level, peace is important for the development of individuals and nations wise also and for the creation of a better foundation and root for the future generation. This type of program can impact effectively enhance and maintain inner peace and understand the cause of conflict and rectify the problem with the calm and care. Its needs to integrate this kind of education into school, college for a better foundation. The researcher also found through the hypothesis after the post-test of Conflict Resolution skills significant difference shows between the experimental group. It shows peace education care, empathy, anger, fighting, and bullying factors students understand the problem roots and collaboration and co-operative how it's needed to manage they explore through the PEP program.

This study also found that the hypothesis after the post-test of Communication Skill significant difference shows for the experimental group. But mean score shows higher for the control group. The dimensions of the communication skill is cognition, Emotional and the Behaviour aspect so because of exam period the result of Experimental group Mean score is less from the control group. Its also understood that the process done after the examination so that's why the effected but students finish this task this is also conflict resolution technique used by students. It can be concluded that if we see the post test result of conflict resolution skill enhance through the peace education program. The findings described above are identical to the literature. (Maurya, Ram Shiromani (2017)) the results of this study was found significant for the dimensions such as truth, love, non-violence, compassion resulting in the peaceful conflict resolution of the students for these dimensions. (Singh, Vikramjit (2012)) Peace education strategy has significant results show in development of attitude towards conflict resolution among adolescent students. And no significant results shows in the sex or class in terms of developing attitude towards conflict resolution among adolescent students. Or no significant effect on sex or class in terms of developing conflict resolution skills among adolescent students. (Ketki Satpute (2019)) the findings there is significant difference is the pre-test score of control group and experimental group of development of culture of pre-test and post-test in dimension of Value and Attitudes. There is no significant difference in the pre-test score of control group and Experimental group of development of culture of peace with respect to dimension "Skills". (Ali Serdar SADKAL Abbas TÜRNÜKLÜ Tarık TOTAN (2012)) Peace Education Program implemented on experiment group was effective in increasing students' empathy levels. Compared to experiment and control groups in terms of gender, both girl and boy students' empathy levels increased in favour of experiment group. (Esmaeil Sadri Damirchi, Filiz Bilge (2014)) Findings of the study are considered to be helpful in directing teachers' and others related authorities' attention to peace and conflict resolution education and in designing other studies with broader scopes. (Esmaeil Sadri Damirchi, Filiz Bilge (2014)) result found that the data analysis was achieved through Covariance statistical test and showed that PEP training had been effective on the conflict resolution and communication skills of students.

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